

ASPECTS TO CONSIDER ACQUIRING OPEN SOURCE OR CLOSED SOURCE SOFTWARE

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Introduction

From time to time, organizations need to acquire new software or reconsider the use of software they already have. One of the challenges they face is whether to employ [open source](#) or [closed source](#) software. Such a choice is not a simple “we are proponents of open source software” or “we are opponents of the products of big tech”. Since every acquisition process is different, no general advice can be given.

A responsible decision involves a number of aspects, which together determine the correct selection for a specific situation. All persons involved with a software product (the stakeholders, e.g. users, application management, organization management, legal counselors) should be involved in this process. Probably this might not be an easy process, because the aspects to consider are often very different, which may make a comparison complicated.

This document lists a number of questions (or aspects) related to open or closed source software acquisition. Answers to these questions may guide stakeholders in making an informed and conscious decision to the best solution for their specific situation. Preferably, all arguments that have been considered in this process are being recorded, so that others may learn from it.

Examples

Examples of products, aspects and consequences of choosing open or closed source software:

- The aspect of end user support.
The supplier of the questionnaire tool [Qualtrics](#) offers support to end users 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, by email, telephone and chat. If stakeholders consider this important, an open source alternative means a considerable adjustment to an organization to be able to offer comparable support.
- The aspect of number of features and cost.
The research information system [Pure](#) has a large number of features. Open source alternatives exist, but they seem to offer less possibilities. Whether this is acceptable or not is the outcome of a discussion between the stakeholders. In addition, the license and hosting costs of Pure are relatively low. Any alternative is likely to result in higher costs.
- The aspect of a “unique” product.
The PhD process administration tool [Hora Finita](#) fits seamlessly into the Dutch PhD process. There is no open source alternative, so similar open source software would have to be developed entirely in-house (possibly in collaboration with other Dutch universities).
- The aspect of ubiquity of technology.
How often software is used and by whom can be an argument to choose it. For ubiquitous technology, advice can be found more easily in user communities. Examples are open source programming languages (e.g. [Perl](#), [PHP](#), [Python](#), [R](#), [Rust](#)), operating systems (e.g. [Linux](#)), web servers (e.g. [Apache](#)), or databases (e.g. [MariaDB](#), [MySQL](#), [Postgres](#)).

When opting for open source, the effort for an organization may increase because people and resources are needed for support, development, administration and hosting.

Aspects

The purpose of the questions (or aspects) in the table below is that by answering them for a specific situation, an overview arises of the consequences of a choice between open or closed source software. This overview can then be used for a discussion between the stakeholders. The table is meant to give guidance: it is not necessary to answer all questions.

Three different situations are considered in the table below: open source software, closed source software, and open source software supported by an external organization. The latter offers the advantage that an organization does not have to set up a support organization itself, but it might not be available for every open source product. For example, for [Learning Management Systems](#), one may choose between resp. [Moodle](#), [Blackboard](#) and [Moodle powered by a Moodle Certified Partner](#).

questions or aspects	space for answers		
	open source software	closed source software	open source supported by an external organization
Related to the product: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does the product support a primary research, education, or business process? If so, how critical is that process in terms of continuity, availability, integrity and confidentiality? • How open is the product? E.g. vendor lock-in, exit scenario, licensing model? • How flexible is the product? E.g. linking/integration with other systems, adaptability to an organization, development roadmap, ease of cooperation with other organizations/consortia? • Is a possible difference in functionality between the open source and closed source product relevant? • How is community support? E.g. administrative support by a community, willingness to develop in a consortium? • How many organizations use the product? • How “unique” is the product? • Is a certified product required? 			
Related to the supplier: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How is the viability of the supplier? E.g. organization size, expertise, certification, start up/market leader/monopolist? • In which country is the supplier located? In which country are the data located and software hosted? 	[supplier is own organization]	[supplier is external organization]	[supplier is external organization, together with own organization]
Related to user support by the supplier: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How are users being supported? E.g. number of hours per day, methods of contact, speed of responses? • How is the user community supported? • How are requests for changes supported? 	[supplier is own organization]	[supplier is external organization]	[supplier is external organization, together with own organization]
Related to administrative support by the supplier: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How is regular and exceptional (i.e. in case of disaster) application management organized (time, manpower)? • What is the update/upgrade process (time, manpower)? • What is the response to security or privacy notifications? 	[supplier is own organization]	[supplier is external organization]	[supplier is external organization, together with own organization]

	space for answers		
questions or aspects	open source software	closed source software	open source supported by an external organization
Related to costs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product (one time, recurring)? • Administrative support (financial, manpower)? • Hosting (financial, manpower)? • Contribution to development (financial, manpower)? 	[costs will be mainly manpower]	[costs will be mainly financial]	[costs are a combination of manpower & financial]

This table does not include all aspects relevant to a software selection process. Some general aspects (equally important but less connected to the consideration of open or closed source software) are: what are the requirements for the product? In what way can it be adapted to an organization, and what are the costs involved? How does it fit in the architecture of an organization? Is it cloud based or to be installed on site? Is a potential product really “unique”? Do the potential users know the preferred product and what do they think of it? Is the product already used in other parts of an organization? Does the product conform to security and privacy requirements? Does an organization remain owner of the data in the system? Does the supplier conform with purchasing conditions?